

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Arařtırmaları Kongresi Tam Metinleri

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مقدمة

يواجه العالم تحديات كبيرة في إقامة توازن بين التنمية المستدامة والحفاظ على البيئة من جهة ومن جهة أخرى تحقيق الأمن الغذائي والذي أصبح من أولويات الدول بفعل الاحتكار واختلال التوازن بين الطلب والإنتاج، ففي الوقت الذي يواصل فيه الاعتماد على الطرق التقليدية في الزراعة المعتمدة أساساً على تساقط الأمطار والاستهلاك المفرط للمياه الجوفية غير المتجددة، فإن هذا له أثراً كبيراً على نضوب الموارد الاقتصادية غير المتجددة واستقرار الأمن الغذائي بالعالم. ولذلك يتجه العالم إلى مصادر الطاقة المتجددة والبحث عن بدائل تضمن احتياجات السكان وفق مبدأ التنمية المستدامة.

وتعد الطاقة المتجددة بأنها الحل الأخير لمشاكل الطاقة والبيئة في العالم، مما يتيح إمكانية الطاقة الرخيصة وغير المحدودة تقريباً الخالية من التلوث، حيث نجد بأن العالم يستهلك الطاقة من مصادر عديدة، فمنها المصادر التي تأتي من خامات الوقود الأحفوري مثل الفحم والنفط والغاز الطبيعي، ومنها الطاقة التي تأتي من مصادر صناعية مثل الطاقة النووية. كما يحصل على الطاقة أيضاً من مصادر طبيعية مثل الطاقة الشمسية والطاقة المستخلصة من الرياح ومساقط المياه والتي تسمى بمصادر الطاقة المتجددة.

إن المشاكل المتفاقمة من خلال أزمات الطاقة والتخوف من احتمال الأمن الغذائي ولا سيما في الدول الأكثر فقراً، يستوجب إعادة التفكير بشكل جوهري على المستوى الدولي وفق استراتيجيات مستدامة تحقق الاستقرار على مستوى العالم وتجنباً الوقوع في أزمات دولية تتركز أساساً على الاستغلال العقلاني للموارد الطبيعية واعتماد طاقات متجددة وأساليب جديدة في الزراعة لضمان تحقيق استدامة في الأمن الغذائي والحفاظ على حقوق الأجيال القادمة.

د. صيد وحمد سفيان

رئيس اللجنة العلمية

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Preface

The world faces great challenges in balancing sustainable development and environmental preservation with achieving food security, which has become a priority for countries due to the monopoly and imbalance between demand and production, while continuing to rely on traditional agricultural methods based mainly on rainfall and excessive consumption of non-renewable groundwater, This has a significant impact on the depletion of non-renewable economic resources and the stability of global food security. Therefore, the world is turning to renewable energy sources and is looking for alternatives that guarantee the needs of the population in accordance with the principle of sustainable development.

Renewable energy promises to be the latest solution to the world's energy and environmental problems, allowing for the possibility of cheap and nearly unlimited energy, free of pollution, as we find that the world consumes energy from many sources, including sources from fossil fuel ores such as coal, oil and natural gas, and energy from industrial sources such as nuclear power. It also draws energy from natural sources such as solar, wind and watersheds called renewable energy sources.

The problems exacerbated by the energy crises and the fear of the occupation of food security, especially in the poorest countries, require a fundamental rethinking at the international level in accordance with sustainable strategies that ensure stability at the global level and avoid falling into international crises based mainly on the rational exploitation of natural resources and the adoption of renewable energies and new methods of agriculture to ensure the sustainability of food security and preservation of the rights of future generations.

Prof. Dr. Sid Ahmed Soufiane

President of the Scientific Committee

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ÖN SÖZ

6. Uluslararası Sürdürülebilir Kalkınma ve Uzay Araştırmaları Kongresi, 08-11 Ekim 2024 tarihlerinde Ankara'da gerçekleşti. Bu kongre, Saybilder Topluluğunun organizasyonunda ve başta Ankara Hacı Bayram Veli Üniversitesi, Mardin Artuklu Üniversitesi, Carthage University olmak üzere çeşitli yükseköğretim kurumlarının ilmi desteği ile düzenlenmektedir. Kongreye 5 farklı ülkeden davetli konuşmacı davet edilmiştir. Aynı zamanda Türkçe, İngilizce ve Arapça duyurular yapılarak bilim insanlarına çağrıda bulunulmuştur. Bu çağrılar sonrasında Türkiye'den 16, Türkiye dışından da 8 ülkeden (Cezayir, Çin, Fas, Libya, Mısır, Suudi Arabistan Krallığı, Tunus, Birleşik Arap Emirlikleri) 53 bildiri yer almaktadır. Tüm bildiriler kör hakemlik sürecinden geçirildikten sonra sunuma kabul veya reddi gerçekleştirilmiştir. Bu süreç içerisinde bildirilerin önemli bir kısmına hakemlerden düzeltme talebi gelmiştir. Hakemler tarafından talep edilen düzeltmelerin yapılıp yapılmadığı da özenle kontrol edilmiş ve düzeltmelerden sonra kabul mektupları düzenlenerek yazarlarına gönderilmiştir. Bu kitapta kongrede sunulan bildirilere ait tam metinler yer almaktadır.

Kongrenin bilim insanları arasındaki iletişimi kuvvetlendirmesini, bilgi alışverişini arttırmasını, ortak çalışma zeminlerini oluşturmasını, milletimize, insanlığa ve bilgiyle amel edenlere faydalı olmasını diliyorum.

Bu kitapta kongrede sunum yapan bilim insanlarının bildirinin tam metinleri yer almaktadır. Kongreye iştirak edemeyen ve bu konulara ilgi duyan kimselerin metinlerden istifade edebilmesini sağlayacak olan bu çalışmanın bilim dünyasına hayırlara vesile olmasını diliyorum.

15.10.2024

Prof. Dr. Şinasi Akdemir

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Signal and Image-Based Data Augmentation to Expand Datasets for Deep Learning Models

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Abstract

Deep learning and artificial intelligence have begun to appear in each branch of science with advances in technologies. The ability of deep learning models to perform, as expected, usually rests on large and varied datasets. However, obtaining datasets, especially in certain fields of medicine and engineering, can be expensive and time-consuming. To overcome this challenge, it is necessary to augment limited amounts of data using various techniques. In this study, an example application of signal and image-based data augmentation techniques is presented to expand datasets for deep learning models. The augmented dataset was tested on a basic Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model, and it was observed that it did not increase the risk of overfitting or error.

Keywords: Data augmentation, signal processing, image processing, dataset expansion

Introduction

Deep learning and artificial intelligence, driven by rapid technological advancements, have found significant applications in various fields such as healthcare, engineering, finance, and education (Goodfellow, 2016; LeCun et al., 2015). In these areas, the learning process is carried out using large volumes of data. However, access to the large and balanced datasets required for the successful application of deep learning models poses a significant challenge, particularly in disciplines like medicine and engineering (Litjens et al., 2017; Szegedy et al., 2015). The high costs and time-intensive nature of data collection processes often result in datasets that are limited in size and diversity.

These difficulties have led researchers to focus on data augmentation techniques. Data augmentation refers to a set of methods used to expand existing datasets and improve the generalization performance of models (Connor Shorten & Taghi M. Khoshgoftaar, 2019). These

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techniques are particularly effective in reducing overfitting and enhancing model performance in environments with limited data. Data augmentation methods used in fields such as signal processing and image processing can improve the accuracy of deep learning models by generating synthetic data that better represents real-world situations (Duong & Nguyen-Thi, 2021; Wang & Perez, 2017).

In these domains, commonly used augmentation techniques are categorized as signal-based and image-based approaches (Felix & Lee, 2019; Goodfellow et al., 2020). One of the most revolutionary models for synthetic data generation is the Generative Adversarial Network (GAN), proposed by Goodfellow (Goodfellow et al., 2020). However, GAN is not the earliest architecture in this field. In 1987, autoencoders capable of generating data were introduced by Lecun (Lecun, 1987). The inclusion of probabilistic models has also continued to yield successful results (Kingma, 2013). Although these networks have achieved notable outcomes, GANs have demonstrated exceptional capabilities, particularly in the field of image generation. Navidan et al. (Navidan et al., 2021), conducted a detailed study on GANs, emphasizing that significant improvements were achieved in enhancing the capabilities of these models.

Signal-based data augmentation is a method specifically used for time series data. This approach aims to generate new examples by modifying existing signals through various mathematical or statistical operations. Augmentation techniques are often preferred due to data privacy concerns or the limited availability of data in this field (Iglesias et al., 2023). In their study, Iwana and Uchida examined data augmentation techniques for time series and their applications in time classification using neural networks, highlighting the characteristics of each augmentation method (Iwana & Uchida, 2021). In recent years, other studies have focused on the classification and manipulation of discrete and continuous time series using GANs (Brophy et al., 2021). Generally, research in this area tends to concentrate on specific models and approaches (Brophy et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2024).

Image-based data augmentation methods are more commonly categorized among traditional approaches and include various basic algorithms such as cropping, scaling, mirroring, and color enhancement (Krizhevsky & Hinton, 2009; Mikołajczyk & Grochowski, 2018; Simonyan, 2014). In his study, Goceri examined data augmentation techniques used to enhance the diagnostic performance of deep learning models for medical images of different organs (Goceri, 2023). Similarly, Fu and colleagues converted 1D bearing vibration fault data into 2D image files by applying wavelet transform. They then applied data augmentation techniques to these image files and conducted experimental studies on the datasets (Fu et al., 2023). Garcea et al. compiled studies conducted with these techniques between 2018 and 2022, producing a comprehensive review article (Garcea et al., 2023).

In this study, the classification performance of a dataset obtained using signal- and image-based data augmentation techniques was evaluated with a basic CNN model. Vibration signals collected from BLDC motor bearings were analyzed in four distinct classes, including healthy and faulty conditions. Due to the limited availability of existing data, synthetic data was generated using both signal processing and image processing techniques. Unlike other methods, the Complete Ensemble Empirical Mode Decomposition with Adaptive Noise (CEEMDAN) technique, commonly used for decomposition and filtering in time series analysis, was employed for signal-based data augmentation. Although the Intrinsic Mode Functions (IMFs) obtained through this method were evaluated separately, the approach of combining them to reconstruct the original signal introduced a novel perspective to signal-

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based data augmentation methods. This approach aimed to improve the generalization capacity of the model by training it with a broader dataset. The results demonstrated the impact of data augmentation techniques on model performance, emphasizing the importance of the data expansion process in deep learning applications.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Dataset

The dataset used in this study was prepared by Loparo (Loparo, 2012) and published on the Case Western Reserve University website (University, 2023). This dataset is widely preferred for diagnosing and classifying bearing faults as well as for training machine learning models. It is detailed to reflect inner race, outer race, and ball faults in bearings under various speed and load conditions and across different fault severity levels.

In this study, the signals representing the healthy state of the bearings, as well as inner race, outer race, and ball faults, were considered as four distinct classes. These signals were recorded at a sampling frequency of 48 kHz.

Figure 4: Raw Signals

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Figure 1 shows the raw forms of signals recorded under different load conditions before any processing. (a) represents the signal from a healthy motor; (b), (c), and (d) display the graphs of faulty signals. Of these (b), ball failure; (c), inner ring failure; (d), outer ring failure.

2.1 Applied Data Augmentation Techniques

2.1.1 Complete Ensemble Empirical Mode Decomposition with Adaptive Noise (CEEMDAN)

This technique was offered as an improvement to the traditional Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) approach for the analysis of non-stationary and non-linear time series. Since EMD focuses on a specific signal range depending on its condition, it may fail to evaluate subsequent parts of the signal. To avoid mode mixing problems, CEEMDAN adds noise to the signal at each stage and updates this noise adaptively, thereby preserving the characteristics of the signals (Huang et al., 1998; Torres et al., 2011). The mathematical algorithm of CEEMDAN is presented as follows (Flandrin et al., 2004; Liu et al., 2021; Owusu Junior et al., 2021; Wu & Huang, 2009).

Adding white noise of different amplitudes to the signal:

- i. $x_k(t) = x(t) + \omega_k(t)$ (1)

- ii. The EMD technique is used in the decomposition process for the first IMF (Intrinsic Mode Functions), as shown in equation (1).

- iii. The mean of the first IMF

$$\overline{IMF_1(n)} = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K IMF_{1k}(t) \quad (2)$$

- iv. The residual signal components are calculated as follows.

$$C_n = \begin{cases} x(t) - IMF_1(n), n = 1, \\ C_{n-1} - IMF_1(n), n > 1. \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

- v. The ρ -th component of the signal after EMD is represented. The subsequent components are calculated as follows:

$$IMF_{(L+1)}(n) = \frac{1}{K} \sum_{k=1}^K E_L \{C_L(t) + \sigma_L E_L(\omega_k(t))\} \quad (4)$$

- vi. Finally, the n stationary components reconstruct the original signal.

$$x(t) = C(t) + \sum_{m=1}^M \overline{IMF_m}(t) \quad (5)$$

Figure 5: IMF image of a healthy signal preprocessed with CEEMDAN

Figure 2 illustrates the step-by-step decomposition of a healthy signal into IMF components using the CEEMDAN method. A total of 22 IMFs were generated for the healthy signal. Additionally, the first signal represents the original signal, while the 22nd signal is referred to as the residual, after which no further IMFs are formed. Figure 3, on the other hand, demonstrates the IMF decomposition of a faulty signal using CEEMDAN. The faulty signal consists of a total of 19 IMFs. In this figure, the first signal represents the raw form of the signal, while the final signal is referred to as the residual.

Figure 6: IMF image of a faulty signal preprocessed with CEEMDAN

2.1.2 Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT)

It is a technique used in time-frequency analysis. The traditional Fourier Transform is employed to analyze the frequency components of a signal but does not provide time information. STFT, on the other hand, was developed to determine both the time and frequency content of a signal (Randall, 1987; Wang et al., 2017; Yeşilyurt et al., 2015). STFT is calculated using the following formula:

$$X_k(t) = \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} x(n) \cdot w(t-n) \cdot e^{-j2\pi kn/N}$$

This formula;

- $X_k(t)$ represents the time-frequency spectrum, which is the output of the STFT.
- $x(n)$ represents the input signal.
- $w(t)$ represents the window function.
- K represents the frequency index.
- N represents the signal length.

The process steps are carried out as follows:

1. The input signal is divided into short time intervals (frames).
2. A window function is applied to each frame.
3. The windowed frame is subjected to a Fourier Transform.
4. The resulting time-frequency spectrum is tracked for all frames.

Although STFT has many advantages in analyzing frequency and time information in the signal together, analyzing variation over time and feature extraction, it has disadvantages such

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as high computational power required for signal processing and noise affecting the results (Wang et al., 2017; Zhang & Deng, 2023).

Figure 7: STFT transformed image of each IMF of the healthy signal

Figure 2 illustrates the IMFs obtained through CEEMDAN, while Figure 4 displays their respective spectrograms. A total of 22 spectrograms are shown in Figure 4. Additionally, the texture relationships between the images can also be observed when examined sequentially from top to bottom.

Figure 8: STFT converted image of each IMF of the faulty signal

In Figure 5, the spectrogram of each IMF of the defective signal decomposed with CEEMDAN in Figure 3 is presented as thumbnails and the number of IMFs is 19.

2.1.3 Data Augmentation

Data augmentation describes a set of techniques that boost the amount of data artificially by creating new data points from existing data points. These techniques introduce small modifications to the original data to create variations. Data augmentation is commonly employed to enhance performance, reduce data collection costs, and better reflect real-world

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scenarios. For image data, it involves operations such as rotation, translation, cropping, noise addition, and blurring, among others (Connor Shorten & Taghi M Khoshgoftaar, 2019).

Figure 9: An example image obtained from signals with different loads for data replication process

Figure 6 shows sample images randomly selected from the four-class dataset after the data augmentation process has been performed.

2.2 Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)

CNN is a widely used and highly successful deep learning model for image classification and recognition problems. It became one of the fundamental architectures of deep learning after the AlexNet model achieved remarkable success in the 2012 ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge (ILSVRC) (Deng et al., 2012; Dhillon & Verma, 2020; Krizhevsky et al., 2012; Shrestha & Mahmood, 2019). CNNs consist of multiple layers, each serving different purposes, to extract feature maps from images. This structure provides virtually unlimited possibilities for experimentation to achieve the best performance (Krizhevsky et al., 2012).

Figure 10: Convolutional Neural Network Architecture

When examining the CNN architecture presented in Figure 7, the feature extraction section uses the Input Layer, Convolutional Layer, and Pooling Layer. In contrast, the classification section is completed through the Fully Connected Layer and other layers connected to it. The working principle of CNNs can be summarized as follows: Data received from the Input Layer is processed in the Convolutional Layer using specific filter sizes (e.g., 3x3, 5x5), and then dimensionality reduction is applied in the Pooling Layer. This reduces the risk of overfitting and decreases computational costs. Next, classification is performed through the Fully Connected Layer. To enhance performance, the Rectified Linear Unit Layer (ReLU Layer) facilitates rapid learning, while the Dropout Layer prevents overfitting by deactivating certain nodes. The classification process is completed through the Output Layer (Classification Layer). The difference between the result obtained from the Fully Connected Layer and the expected value is calculated using a gradient-based backpropagation algorithm, which optimizes the network weights. The training process ends when the specified number of epochs is reached or when stopping criteria are met (Goodfellow et al., 2016; Özkan & Ülker, 2017; Wang et al., 2017).

3. Experimental Study and Results

This study investigated the impact of data augmentation techniques on the classification of bearing faults in BLDC motors using CNN. The dataset creation process was carried out as follows: The 1D raw signal was decomposed into IMFs using the CEEMDAN method, which differs from traditional filtering and data augmentation approaches. Each IMF signal was treated under the assumption that it retains the texture of the original signal and can reconstruct the original signal when combined. Following this approach, each IMF signal obtained during the process was transformed into a spectral 2D image format using the STFT method. For each spectrogram, the signal frequency was set to 48 kHz. The window size was chosen as 256, and a Hamming window was used to minimize leakage around the main lobe by reducing the amplitude of the side lobes. The overlap amount was set to 128, which is half of the window size. Subsequently, data augmentation techniques were applied to increase the diversity of the images. These techniques included operations such as rotation, translation, noise addition, cropping, blurring, and color modification. Data augmentation processes were applied randomly and independently, resulting in different image files. Table 1 presents the classes and the number of samples in the augmented dataset.

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Table 1: Increased number and classes of data sets

	Health	Ball Fault	Inner Race Fault	Outer Race Fault	Total
Numbers of Image	3476	3294	3294	3294	13358

The obtained images were standardized into pixel matrices with dimensions of 64x64x3. During the resizing process, antialiasing was applied for edge smoothing to preserve image quality, and bicubic interpolation was used to ensure smooth transitions between pixels.

Table 2: Layer structure of the CNN model used for training and testing

#	Layer Type	Parameters/Notes
1	imageInputLayer	Input size: 64x64x3
2	convolution2dLayer	Filter Size: 3 × 3, Num Filters: 256
3	reluLayer	-
4	convolution2dLayer	Filter Size: 3 × 3, Num Filters: 256
5	reluLayer	-
6	maxPooling2dLayer	Pool Size: 2 × 2, Stride: 2
7	convolution2dLayer	Filter Size: 3 × 3, Num Filters: 256
8	reluLayer	-
9	convolution2dLayer	Filter Size: 3 × 3, Num Filters: 256
10	reluLayer	-
11	maxPooling2dLayer	Pool Size: 2 × 2, Stride: 2
12	fullyConnectedLayer	Output Size: 512
13	reluLayer	-
14	dropoutLayer	Dropout Probability: 0.5
15	fullyConnectedLayer	Output Size: 2
16	softmaxLayer	-
17	classificationLayer	-

This 4-class dataset was used to train a basic CNN model. The layer structure of the model is presented in Table 2. The model includes a block consisting of two consecutive convolution and ReLU layers followed by a max pooling layer. Next, there is a fully connected layer (512

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neurons) and a dropout layer (0.5), which is a commonly used configuration in classic CNN architectures. The maxPooling2dLayer after each block reduces the spatial dimensions by half, keeping the number of parameters and computational load under control. From this perspective, the model can be considered a basic CNN that is easy to train and interpret.

Table 3: The hyperparameter values used

Parameters	Value
Optimizer	Sgdm
Epoch	50
Mini Batch Size	32
Initial Learn Rate	0.001
Max Epoch	50

The hyperparameters of the model are provided in Table 3. To statistically evaluate the model's performance in a meaningful way, it was retrained 10 times. This approach aimed to minimize the random variability of results by conducting multiple trials, ensuring a more reliable assessment of the performance metrics.

Figure 11: Accuracy Loss graph of the model

The Accuracy and Loss graph for the model is shown in Figure 8. When examining the accuracy graph from the training process, it is observed that the model initially had a very low accuracy level (around 5-10%) but learned rapidly as training progressed. During the first few thousand iterations, the accuracy sharply increased, reaching approximately 90%. In subsequent iterations, the model's accuracy exceeded 98%, and the curve leveled off, indicating stability. Looking at the loss graph, the error value, which was initially very high (around ~14), decreased rapidly. As the training progressed, the loss value approached 0 and

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stabilized at a low level in the final iterations. This indicates that the model learned very effectively on the training data.

Figure 12: Model's confusion matrix

The confusion matrix for the model is shown in Figure 9. The confusion matrix illustrates the model's performance by analyzing the classification accuracy between BallFault, Health, InnerFault, and OuterFault. On average, the performance rate of the proposed model was approximately 81.8%, with the best rate in class Health with Recall-92.5% and precision-80.1%. The lowest, or weakest, performance was recorded for InnerFault, whose Recall equaled 89.2 and precision was 75.0%. In the InnerFault class, the misclassification rate was 25%, indicating that the model made more errors in this class compared to others. Similarly, notable misclassification rates were observed in the BallFault (25.8% failure) and OuterFault (24.3% failure) classes. While the model performed very well in the Health class, it struggled more with distinguishing the InnerFault and OuterFault classes. This suggests that the model experienced more confusion between these two classes, possibly due to their similar characteristics.

Table 4: Values of metrics

Metric name	Value (%)
Accuracy	0.81849
Precision	0.81849
Recall	0.81849
F1 Score	0.81849

Considering some of the key metrics to assess the performance of classification done by a model, accuracy, precision, recall, and F1 score are all found to be 81.8%. Accuracy, in this

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case, is also 81.8%, showing the overall rate at which the model correctly predicted all classes. Precision, also 81.8%, indicates the likelihood that instances predicted to belong to a specific class truly belong to that class. Recall, at 81.8%, measures the model's ability to identify all instances of a specific class. The F1 score, which is also 81.8%, provides a balanced measure of precision and recall. When these metrics are equal, it suggests that the model performs consistently and in a balanced manner across all classes.

4. Conclusion

In this study, a 1D dataset consisting of four classes – one healthy and three faulty – obtained from a BLDC motor was expanded using signal- and image-based augmentation techniques and classified using the deep learning method CNN. Unlike traditional approaches, signal-based data augmentation was performed using the CEEMDAN method. The expanded dataset was trained on a basic CNN model, and the model's accuracy was determined to be 81 %.

The results of the study suggest that incorporating different signal processing techniques during the signal-based data augmentation phase and employing various data augmentation strategies could further enhance model performance. Additionally, applying image-based data augmentation methods, optimizing hyperparameters, and using weighting strategies to address class imbalances are other important approaches that could improve the model's classification accuracy.

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